

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Abdumannopov Kamronbek G'ayratjon o'g'li

BUDJET TIZIMI BYUDJETLARI IJROSI NAZORATNING SHAKLLARI VA USULLARI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/FEVRAL

